

**Entrepreneuring after 50: The liminal identity transitions of
older emergent entrepreneurs**

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship has been proposed as a solution to extending working lives. However, little is known about how older (50+) emergent entrepreneurs (OEE) manage their personal transitions into entrepreneurship. In this paper, we propose to use a liminal identity work perspective to explore the identity paradoxes that OEE experience during their transition into entrepreneurship and how they manage it. We use a qualitative study conducted over 14 months in the U.K. Our analysis shows how OEE confront identity paradoxes, interruptions and identity polarization in their attempts to shift older identities and activity patterns into new ones. OEE who manage to overcome the identity interruptions and polarization that the transition brings, move away from an initial sense of isolation and bring creative understandings to older entrepreneuring processes. Our results expand our current understanding of the process of entrepreneurial identity work in liminal conditions, especially among OEE, by looking at the tensions emerging between potentially new and customary identities and behaviours as an important aspect of entrepreneuring transitions rather than as negative frictions to be avoided.

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurship is being proposed as a solution to extending working lives in the context of an increasingly ageing population (Flynn et al. 2014; Maltby 2011; World Economic Forum 2018). Older (50+) people also face challenges of late life (un)employment, retirement and pension shortfalls due to the recent changes in employer-sponsored pension schemes and the declining value of personal savings (Bukodi 2017; Kibler et al. 2015). However, while older entrepreneurship is seen as a 'silver lining' to an older, non-contributing population (Stirzaker and Galloway 2017), and many older people have to work longer due to their ongoing need for an income (Moulton and Scott 2014), older workers are still discriminated against in society and the labour market (Riach and Loretto 2009). Thus, as the recent economic crisis and recession have forced changes in outlook and attitude towards older workers (Thomas et al. 2014), OEE find themselves in the paradoxical situation of being encouraged to take on the risks associated with starting up a business while still suffering social exclusion in a context of increasing economic uncertainty (Kibler et al. 2015).

'Older entrepreneurship' is becoming one of the identity paradoxes typical of current work conditions, such as having to 'be creative' and to 'play when at work' (Andersen 2013) or to 'manage successfully' one's 'ageing' (Rozanova 2010). While the paradoxical nature of these identity directives has been clearly identified (Putnam et al. 2016), the implications of living in paradox and trying to overcome it in generative ways have rarely been addressed, particularly in the case of OEE. A paradox lens on entrepreneurial identity transformation would enable a more

1
2 holistic, fluid, both/and framing of the tensions encountered by older entrepreneurs (Beech et al.
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4 2004; Lewis 2000). Furthermore, OEE find themselves confronting a situation where an existing
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6 identity and social position is suspended (or becomes unviable) and a new one is not yet in place.
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8 We propose, therefore, to use a liminal approach to entrepreneurial identity development to better
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10 understand how OEE navigate identity paradoxes in their personal transitions towards
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12 entrepreneurship.
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16 Our paper contributes to the emergent research tradition that frames entrepreneurship as a
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18 temporary and evolving process (Steyaert 2007; Steyaert and Hjorth 2006), and entrepreneurial
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20 identities as developed through the on-going engagement of entrepreneurs with their context (Essers
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22 and Benchop 2007; Mallett and Wapshott 2015) and enacted in identity narratives (Hamilton 2014;
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24 Jones et al. 2008). We also respond to recent calls (Leitch and Harrison 2016) for entrepreneurial
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26 identity research to move beyond the dominant emphasis on essentialist notions of identity-as-entity
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28 to more process-oriented views. We add to this research tradition by framing entrepreneurial
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30 identity development as a liminal and transformative condition, a process of creating possible
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32 futures and states of being. In this regard, we understand liminality as a condition of paradoxical
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34 'in-between' identities and social positions that can prompt OEE to develop new identity
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36 possibilities, ultimately altering their current patterns of activity.
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40 We explore the personal transitions into entrepreneurship of OEE by using a qualitative study
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42 conducted over 14 months in the U.K. Through the analysis of 55 in-depth interviews, observations
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44 and documents, we show how OEE manage their liminal condition and the paradoxes it generates
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46 through the process of identity work, that is, through the range of activities they engage in to create,
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48 present, and sustain personal identities congruent with a self-concept (Sveningsson and Alvensson
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50 2003). We develop previous identity work studies in entrepreneurship (Leitch and Harrison 2016;
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52 Phillips et al. 2013), highlighting the importance of the positions OEE take and assign to others
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54 (van Langenhove and Harré 1999) when describing their transition. Our analysis shows how OEE
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56 confront identity paradoxes, interruptions, and identity polarization when attempting to shift
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1 identities and activity patterns in liminal conditions. Our liminal approach to identity transitions
2 captures those identity paradoxes and enables us to understand better how OEE manage the
3 transition from employee to 'older entrepreneur'. For those who manage to overcome the identity
4 interruptions and polarization that the transition brings, there are indications of initial identity and
5 behavioural pattern shifts, as they move away from an initial sense of isolation and are able to bring
6 in a creative understanding of what it is to be an OEE. Our research illustrates the adaptive and
7 fluid nature of the narratives and practices involved in emergent entrepreneuring, and underscore
8 the fluidity, and the on-going and piecemeal everyday work, of such organizing processes. Our
9 research also complements current liminal entrepreneuring studies by looking at the tensions
10 emerging between potentially new and customary identities and behaviours as an important aspect
11 of entrepreneuring transitions rather than as negative frictions to be avoided. These results expand
12 current understanding of the process of entrepreneurial identity work in liminal conditions,
13 especially among OEE.

14 Our paper is structured as follows. We begin by outlining the notion of liminal identity work
15 among OEE underpinning our research. Then, we introduce the case study and the research method.
16 Thereafter, we present our findings in the form of liminal identity work narratives, before
17 concluding with a discussion of our findings and the contributions of our study.

18 **2. Background literature**

19 ***2.1. Becoming an older emergent entrepreneur***

20 The understanding of the process of becoming an entrepreneur has evolved from a focus on
21 individual traits and decision-making into something more relational and embedded (de Clercq and
22 Voronov 2009). Gartner (1988) famously stressed that it is the actions of the individual, rather than
23 individual characteristics, that define someone as being entrepreneurial. However, beyond the
24 instrumental view of 'you are what you do', the focus nowadays is more on relationally oriented
25 understandings of what it is to be an entrepreneur, where entrepreneurial identity is understood as

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2 developed through the on-going engagement of entrepreneurs with their context (Essers and
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4 Benchop 2007; Mallett and Wapshott 2015). Thus, rather than a fixed attribute of the individual,
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6 identity is considered as a constant and emergent project (Sveningsson and Alvensson 2003) and an
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8 aspect of relational and situated processes. Following this perspective, current research describes
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10 being an entrepreneur as a hybrid set of functional activities, societal myths and metaphors
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12 (Drakopoulou-Dodd and Anderson 2007), as well as expectations and responsibilities defined by
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14 different social settings, such as family, community or local industry sector (Nicholson and
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16 Anderson 2005). However, emergent entrepreneurs often lack the efficacy associated with having
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18 prior entrepreneurial experience (Dew et al. 2009) and are challenged to develop an entrepreneurial
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20 identity without experiential knowledge of what that identity means and of what a social position as
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22 entrepreneur entails.
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27 OEE are usually considered as different from other entrepreneurs, for instance, they are seen as
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29 less engaged in risk-taking and opportunity seeking behaviour than younger entrepreneurs (Singh
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31 and DeNoble 2003). On the plus side, older entrepreneurs are usually portrayed as older people in
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33 good health, with enough financial assets to provide working capital for a business, having
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35 developed social capital and networks, and relatively unconstrained by, for example, family
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37 responsibilities (Levesque and Minniti 2006). On the negative side, OEE are portrayed as reluctant
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39 to bear the real risks of entrepreneurship or to assume responsibility for potential business failure
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41 and its personal consequences (Dannreuther and Perren 2013), along with finding it difficult to
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43 secure support, such as investment or mentors (Davies et al. 2016). As a result, while there is
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45 increasing recognition that older entrepreneurs are a varied group (Kautonen et al. 2014), older
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47 entrepreneuring is nevertheless generally seen as 'less efficient' than 'normal' entrepreneuring
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49 (Jayawarna et al. 2013; Mallett and Wapshott 2015).
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55 As Ainsworth and Hardy (2008: 402) suggest, "the enterprising self is an aged construction... not
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57 accessible to all age groups". Therefore, it is not surprising that, despite their increasing importance,
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59 little is known about how OEE manage their personal identity transitions into entrepreneurship. But,
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2 as we become more aware that we cannot afford to ‘throw away’ these human resources (Burke et
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4 al. 2013), we need to close the clear gap between understanding how to better support OEE in their
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6 transitions and our current attitudes and policies. Our research addresses this gap by exploring the
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8 transition into entrepreneurship among OEE from a liminal and narrative identity work perspective.
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10 The linguistic metaphor of identity work seems especially useful in capturing the dynamic
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12 aspects and constant struggles of identity construction in complex and fragmented contexts, such as
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14 the liminal state OEE find themselves in (Brown 2015; Leitch and Harrison 2016; Phillips et al.
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16 2013). Identity work has been defined as the set of processes through which people develop
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18 narratives of the self in a context where external influences seek to impact on, or regulate, the
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20 nature of that self-meaning (Alvesson 2010). The process of identity work enables the weaving of
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22 social and personal identities, joining internal self-reflection with an outward engagement (Watson
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24 2008), as it involves “people being engaged in forming, repairing, maintaining, strengthening or
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26 revising the constructions that are productive of a sense of coherence and distinctiveness”
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28 (Sveningsson and Alvesson 2003: 1165).
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34 A distinct characteristic of identity work is that identities are understood as temporary,
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36 negotiated and contested in on-going internal soliloquies and social interactions (Alvesson et al.
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38 2008; Beech 2011), being continually crafted in changing contexts (Watson 2008). Identity work,
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40 therefore, allows us to explore “identities-in-action and unpick processes of continuity and change”
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42 in identity development (Brown 2015: 33). Beyond inner dialogues, however, identity work also
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44 looks at how particular images, narratives and activities become imbued with meaning and are
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46 taken or rejected as being part of one’s identity. Thus, identity work is also a process of absorbing,
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48 personalising and enacting general narratives (Bamberg 2011) or being constrained by them
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50 (Mallett and Wapshott 2015).
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55 The narrative approach to identity work we use in our research sees identity as held in repertoires
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57 of co-existing self-narratives to be selectively used in response to the context and purpose of
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59 particular practices and interactions (Toyoki and Brown 2014). We further this view by
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2 emphasising the significance of the perspective and the position the author takes in each narrative
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4 (Boje and Smith 2010). When OEE position themselves in entrepreneuring narratives, they produce
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6 a particular self (Davies and Harré 1990) infused with the voices of the generalised ‘other’, making
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8 the positioning of the self in the narrative a joint relational effort between self, other and context
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10 (van Langenhove and Harré 1999). The positions that OEE take and assign to others in these
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12 narratives relate also to particular images, narratives and practices of entrepreneurship through
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14 which they ‘do’ and ‘redo’ entrepreneuring (Steyaert 2007). As such, as the OEE’s narrative
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16 position changes, their perception of entrepreneuring, along with the way they act, changes too.
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18 This multi-voiced nature of the entrepreneurial self is an adaptive response to the fractured social
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20 world we traverse (Gioia and Thomas 1996), explaining its critical relevance in liminal contexts
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22 such as the ones our OEE face.

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27 Identity work seems particularly necessary in liminal conditions, where strains and tensions
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29 prompting feelings of confusion, contradiction and self-doubt leading to an examination of the self
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31 are prevalent (Beyer and Hannah 2002; Lutgen-Sandvik 2008). We now move to outline this
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33 liminal identity process.
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39 ***2.2. Identity paradox in OEE liminal transitions***

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41 In organization studies, the concept of liminality has been treated primarily as a structurally
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43 imposed condition by virtue of a profession or a particular role, e.g., temporary workers (Garsten
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45 1999), consultants (Czarniawska and Mazza 2003), or those undergoing work and role changes
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47 (Daskalaki and Simosi 2018; Ibarra and Obodaru 2016), and is often associated with having
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49 negative consequences. In entrepreneurial terms, liminality has been used more positively to
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51 indicate transformative stages (García-Lorenzo et al. 2018), or spaces, that allow entrepreneurs to
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53 discover their true selves (Brooker and Joppe 2013), where new, possible futures, not yet formed,
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55 exist side-by-side with current trajectories (Henfridsson and Yoo 2014). Thus, a few studies have
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57 started to outline how liminal conditions can prompt emergent entrepreneurs to develop new
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possibilities with a view to ultimately altering current patterns of activity.

The term 'liminal' was first used by van Gennep (1960) to name the middle phase of a rite of passage. Rites of passage are enacted at culturally and socially significant points of transition, such as when moving from childhood to adulthood, from single to married status, or from active employee to retired person, with each category outlining identities and clear areas of social activities. Effectively, van Gennep (1960: 13) distinguishes 'critical' movements within areas of social activity (e.g., being employed in different roles and organizations) from 'liminal' movements between those areas (e.g., between employment and entrepreneurship). With respect to the latter, he identified a typical three-phase pattern of movement that begins with rites of separation (the ceremonial end of a previous identity and social position) and ends with rites of aggregation (when a new identity and social position are ritualistically adopted). But, between these two phases, we find a liminal phase concerned purely with transition.

Liminal rites are transitional, stressing paradoxical 'betwixt and between' qualities, where identities, rules and conventions usually delimiting patterns of social activity are temporarily suspended, hence enabling new becomings (Turner 1977). Turner (1977) referred to these fluid liminal moments as 'anti-structural', emphasizing the opposition of the liminal condition to clear and articulated social structures and norms. A liminal condition implies, therefore, a processual understanding of human collectives, where, for every identity and social position (already a conjointly enacted process), there is a transition, highlighting the generative dynamic through which relatively stable identities and social positions are continuously created, replenished and transformed.

We consider liminality, however, as more than just a feature of rites of passage. In its more abstract and general sense, we understand liminality as referring to a condition of ontological indeterminacy at play in occasions of transition, in the phase where an existing identity and social position is suspended (or becomes unviable) and a new one is not yet in place. During the course of 'untroubled' transitions, identities and social positions that differ from the known patterns can soon

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2 be reconstructed and aggregated into new identities and social positions. However, in periods of
3
4 liminality ‘what comes next’ (van Gennep 1960) is highly unpredictable and requires engaging with
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6 paradox through on-going identity work. In this sense, the concept of liminality describes perfectly
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8 the condition OEE find themselves in when transitioning towards entrepreneurship. OEE experience
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10 and have to manage transitional episodes of ‘troubled’ becoming, where they face on-going anxiety
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12 and fear but also potentially a period of enhanced creativity.
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16 An important characteristic of the ‘liminal’ condition as an ‘interstructural space’ is that it is
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18 paradoxically defined by what it is not (Turner 1977). Turner clearly pointed to the general sense of
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20 confusion and ambiguity that he found typical of this initiatory mid-state. Normally incompatible
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22 elements of the conditions, in between which the interstructural state is found, will be paradoxically
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24 juxtaposed and recombined (Turner 1977). Every element of existence may be found severed from
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26 its usual context, juxtaposed by its usually mutually exclusive opposite, and assembled into new,
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28 totally nonsensical combinations. Thus, all the usual social states of gender, age, and hierarchy may
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30 be negated and reverted in the liminal state. Our liminal approach to entrepreneurial identity
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32 transitions aims to capture those identity paradoxes characteristic of the initiatory mid-state of
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34 liminality to better understand how OEE navigate the transition from employee to ‘older
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36 entrepreneur’.
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40 Paradox has been defined as “the simultaneous presence of contradictory, even mutually
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42 exclusive, elements” (Quinn and Cameron 1988: 2). In traditional managerial views, paradox is
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44 regarded as a dysfunctional state to be eliminated, often looking for resolution by choosing one of
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46 the extremes of a paradox (e.g., Ansoff 1991, 1994; Ansoff et al. 1970; Bettis and Hitt 1995). But,
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48 by seeking to resolve paradoxes, organizations and individuals risk falling into “simplicity traps”
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50 (Lewis 2000: 765), removing the complications that support more innovative performance (Weick
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52 1979). Thus, although choosing among competing tensions might aid short-term performance, a
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54 paradox perspective argues that long-term sustainability can only be achieved through continuous
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56 efforts to meet multiple, divergent demands (Lewis 2000). To favour a preferred pole of a paradox
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to the neglect of its opposite can spur negative and vicious dynamics (Lewis 2000).

Once rendered salient, paradoxical identity tensions stimulate responses. According to paradox studies, responses fuel reinforcing cycles that can be negative or positive (Lewis 2000). Negative, vicious cycles, stem from such factors as cognitive and behavioural forces for consistency, emotional anxiety and defensiveness, and institutional forces for inertia (Cialdini et al. 1995). Individuals may also react by choosing one agenda, altering their beliefs or actions to enable a consistent response (Cialdini et al. 1995), or maintaining a mindless commitment to previous identities and behaviours to enable consistency between past and future (Weick 1993). Such commitments become reinforced by social dynamics that embed inertia in structures (Henderson and Clark 1990), routines (Eisenhardt and Martin 2000) and/or processes where the future becomes wedded to the past. Together, these individual and social forces for consistency fuel a reinforcing cycle by increasingly focusing on a single choice.

A more positive response to paradoxical tensions is the ‘virtuous’ cycle, where awareness of tensions triggers a strategy of acceptance rather than defensiveness (Lüscher and Lewis 2008). Acceptance encourages actors to embrace or “live with” paradox (Lewis 2000), which implies that actors shift their expectations for rationality and linearity to accept paradoxes as persistent and unsolvable puzzles. Acceptance also entails viewing tensions as an invitation for creativity and opportunity (Beech et al. 2004). Through engaging in the opposing alternatives, it is possible to discover the link between them and find meaning to the apparent contradictions.

To sum up, a liminal condition among OEE can be seen as a transition from one status to another (Czarniawska and Mazza 2003) or as a ‘limbo of statuslessness’ (Turner 1977) on a journey towards new roles and understandings. This has implications for how OEE understand subjectivities through blurred, paradoxical or transitional identities. On this basis, a liminal condition, such as that which OEE experience, can contribute to a sense of uncertainty over identities, positions and routines as individuals find themselves divorced from existing structures and known ways of ‘doing and being’. These uncertainties and ambiguities may be exacerbated by the frequent siting in the

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2 margins, tainted by low status and exclusion.

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4 Our research moves away from considering older entrepreneurs as a homogeneous ‘deficient’
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6 group, and explores how these individuals manage their liminal transition into entrepreneurship. We
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8 draw on paradox theory to understand the paradoxical nature of OEE identity transitions, and how
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10 they are confronted and can be creatively dealt with in everyday entrepreneuring. We describe this
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12 process below.
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17 18 **3. Methodology**

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20 Identity, as Berger and Luckmann (1967: 195) argue, “remains unintelligible unless it is located in a
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22 world”, and our interest in liminal identity work narratives is allied with the domain of older
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24 entrepreneurship. Older people increasingly have to develop alternatives to tackle challenges of late
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26 life retirement or pension shortfalls through self-employment and entrepreneurship (Kibler et al.
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28 2015). The U.K. is an example of this trend, with the country’s Office for National Statistics (2019)
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30 noting some 15 per cent of the U.K. workforce, or 4.5 million people, were self-employed as of
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32 2019. Of these, 43 per cent are over 50, while the number over 65 doubled since the 2008 global
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34 financial crisis. Although the U.K. Government is notably concerned about the financial burden the
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36 (non-employed) aged represent for the state, very little support exists for older people to become
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38 economically active (Kautonen et al. 2014). Therefore, to understand the experiences of OEE
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40 undergoing the transition into entrepreneurship, we have used a qualitative research design. We
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42 generated 55 in-depth interviews with OEE in the U.K., and we gathered publicly available
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44 documents and public narratives of entrepreneurship. Our aim is to straddle the micro-macro
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46 boundary (Dawson and Hjorth 2012), looking at OEE personal experiences within the current social
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48 and historical U.K. context.
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54 55 **3.1. Data generation**

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57 Over a period of 14 months, we interviewed 55 OEE, using established entrepreneurship networks
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1 —PRIME¹ (a charitable organisation supporting 50+ entrepreneurs), KPI² (a commercial
2 entrepreneurial development programme), and PENNA³ (a company that provides redundancy
3 programmes for large organisations) — and personal contacts and networks, to generate the
4 interviews. The interviews were conducted in various public and institutional places, as well as in
5 individuals' homes when no other location was available. The average interview length was 60
6 minutes —the longest was 2 hours and the shortest 40 minutes— and every interview was tape-
7 recorded and followed ethical guidelines. During the in-depth interview process, we asked
8 participants about their transition from different (un)employment conditions towards
9 entrepreneurship, as well as their experiences as emergent entrepreneurs, focusing on generating
10 personal 'pre-histories' (Sarasvathy et al. 2010), the non-completed narratives that address
11 transitions, doubts, and unfinished processes.

12 Our main criterion for interviewee selection was the length of time OEE have been trying to set
13 up a business, such that our sample consists of very recent new business owners. In selecting our
14 participants, we followed the GEM (Xavier et al. 2013: 19) classification of new business owners as
15 those who have been in the process of business creation for more than three months, but less than
16 42 months. For our interviewees, the time spent trying to set up a business ranges from 3 months to
17 36 months.

18 Interviewees comprised both recently unemployed and those working previously, and they came
19 from a wide range of backgrounds, with different educational levels and professional working
20 experiences. Most of them were living and working in the London area at the time of interview,
21 with a few (10) coming from the Midlands. We did not discriminate in terms of the products or
22 services our interviewees offer (which range from business consultancy to music therapy) and we

23 1 http://businessofselfemployment.co.uk/?page_id=4222

24 2 <http://www.keypersonofinfluence.com/>

25 3 <http://www.penna.com/>

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2 have a reasonably balanced sample in terms of gender (31 males and 24 females). Our sample
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4 includes entrepreneurs who set up on their own (sole traders), as well as those who started with a
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6 partnership of some kind. In terms of age, most of our OEE were between 49 and 65 years old: the
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8 youngest was 49, while the oldest and still active entrepreneur we interviewed was 83 at the time of
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10 interview.
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13 In addition, 45 out of a total of 500 documents —representing policy documents, public reports,
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15 and media articles— were selected for relevance and analysed. We collected stories on older people
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17 and entrepreneurship in three of the top 20 prominent national newspapers in terms of circulation,
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19 selecting those with clearly differentiated political and financial outlooks and expertise to get a
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21 broad view (*Financial Times*, *The Guardian* and *Daily Mail*). The newspaper articles were selected
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23 based on the completeness and relevance of the stories they described (e.g., referred to OEE in the
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25 U.K., including the social, institutional, or personal challenges they faced in trying to become
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27 entrepreneurs). Article searches were made directly on each newspaper’s own archive. Different
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29 filters were used as each newspaper had its own categories, e.g., ‘employment for older people’,
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31 ‘U.K. self-employment’, ‘U.K. self-employment for older people’, etc. Results were scrutinised and
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33 reduced to include articles between 2009 and 2016 relating mainly to ‘over 50 self-employment’
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35 and ‘U.K. self-employment / entrepreneurship’. Out of a total of 484 media articles explored, we
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37 selected 29 as particularly relevant to our research question for analysis.
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43 The 16 publicly available documents selected refer to government entrepreneurship policy, as
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45 well as Eurofound and GEM (E.U. and U.K.) reports, from 2009 (after the financial crisis when
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47 Government policies for entrepreneurship changed in the U.K.) to 2016 (when our study finished).
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49 We looked for government policies and initiatives supporting entrepreneurship and relevant
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51 legislation affecting older entrepreneurs, such as ‘age discrimination’ and ‘new state pension age’.
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53 Policies and initiatives from 2009 to 2016, such as the ‘New Enterprise Allowance’, ‘Growth
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55 Accelerator’, ‘Work Programme’, ‘Angel CoFund’, and ‘SEED Enterprise Investment Scheme’,
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57 were downloaded from government websites. The use of different methods of data collection
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1 enabled the inclusion of different viewpoints to refine our understanding of the phenomenon under
2 study.
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5 6 7 8 **3.2. Data analysis**

9 All interviews were digitally recorded and transcribed verbatim for thematic and narrative analysis
10 using NVivo and followed inductive and deductive approaches and quality indicators to meet
11 required qualitative research standards (Gioia et al. 2013). All researchers participated in this
12 codification process and common work was carried out to interpret the data. The media articles and
13 government policy documents were also thematically analysed together with the interviews in
14 NVivo to examine the ways in which public narratives present and frame the process of
15 entrepreneuring, shaping institutional and organisational policies and practices that impact the way
16 people respond to the difficulties they face at the symbolic, sociocultural, institutional, and practical
17 level. The GEM and Eurofound reports were used as supporting evidence throughout the analysis.
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32 The data was analysed in two stages. First, we conducted a full thematic analysis with all
33 interviews and documents to identify and analyse patterns of meaning across our dataset. This
34 analysis also enabled us to obtain: general knowledge about differences and similarities in the
35 entrepreneuring process; challenges that OEE face; OEE's daily engagement with the
36 entrepreneuring process; OEE's routines and practices; and the different entrepreneuring
37 interactions OEE reported as experiencing. These themes, among others, were included in the
38 coding framework as first order concepts (Gioia et al. 2013). Second order themes emerged as our
39 analysis uncovered the 'liminal' (Turner 1977) transition OEE undergo: first, separating from a
40 previous clear professional identity and position in their social structure; second, living in an
41 unstructured social and personal period of uncertainty or 'liminal period'; to third, in few cases,
42 starting to outline a new identity and social position as entrepreneurs.
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56 After obtaining an overall view of how interviewees understood the different stages of their
57 liminal transition into entrepreneuring, we sought to identify particular identity struggles and their
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2 links to concrete entrepreneuring practices through a second analysis. For this second analysis, we
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4 followed organisational identity research that theorises identities as texts constructed through
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6 language, discourses and narratives (Harré et al. 2009). We focused on personal narratives, where
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8 OEE described the process of entrepreneuring and positioned themselves within particular
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10 entrepreneuring events in relation to other significant actors (Riessman 2008), as well as within
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12 local and wider discourses that justified and sustained their positioning. The personal stories
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14 illustrated OEE's ability to (re)produce and (re)create identities through identity work (McAdams
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16 and McLean 2013). The narrative analysis was conducted with all the textual material generated in
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18 the data collection.
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23 Within each personal narrative, we identified three main identity tensions, which, following the
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25 literature on identity paradox, we call 'confronting paradox', 'interruption and polarization', and
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27 'pattern shift'. The way OEE described the uncertain and ambiguous experience of transition
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29 towards entrepreneurship is indeed akin to encountering a paradox. In our OEE case, the paradox
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31 arose from attending to the requirements of mutually incompatible identities and social positions
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33 (e.g., employee and entrepreneur). OEE also report that living in a liminal state and encountering an
34
35 identity paradox confuses and interferes with their flows of activity, generating an interruption e.g.,
36
37 being an employee has certain activity requirements that get 'interrupted' when one becomes
38
39 unemployed. In trying to escape their predicament of indeterminacy, OEE forge a solution that
40
41 conforms to discourses and social positions they are caught between, generating a polarization of
42
43 discourses and activities, e.g., OEE try to regain 'employability' by 'becoming young again', while
44
45 stressing their experience in a field. When the identity paradox they encounter cannot easily be
46
47 escaped using existing resources, it seems to push those involved towards the development of new
48
49 identities, social positions and practices within which the paradox can be re-signified. We refer to
50
51 this as the possibility of a pattern shift.
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56 Once the identity tensions in each personal liminal story were identified, we focused on making
57
58 explicit the process of liminal identity work. Turning points in each narrative were identified; these
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1
2 were moments where OEE indicated a pattern shift in the course of the process of entrepreneuring
3
4 and identity positioning. We also identified a main image of entrepreneurship in each narrative that
5
6 provided a unifying narrative theme. This further analysis allowed us to identify the different
7
8 positions that OEE assign to themselves and others, and their effect on how they see the process of
9
10 entrepreneuring.
11

12 13 14 15 16 **4. Findings — Narratives of Older Emergent Entrepreneuring**

17
18 In what follows, we illustrate how our interviewees articulate the process of emergent
19
20 entrepreneurship through narrating their encounters with paradox, interruptions, and potential
21
22 pattern shifts. The narratives also show how our OEE position themselves in their entrepreneuring
23
24 narratives while engaging in identity work, and manage identity tensions, both discursively and
25
26 practically, during their liminal transition process. Table 1 summarizes the key narrative identity
27
28 tensions and liminal dimensions that emerged from our analysis.
29
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31

32 -----
33 Table 1 about here
34 -----

35 36 **4.1. Confronting paradox: Between identity continuity and innovation**

37
38 The process of leaving an organization or giving up a professional identity is often associated with
39
40 difficult transition periods. Most people, when facing an end to their careers, must give up a valued
41
42 position, a close work relationship, team membership, or a cherished work location (Hoyer and
43
44 Steyaert 2015). According to Conroy and O’Leary-Kelly (2014: 67), these losses can generate “a
45
46 liminal state between letting go of the old and moving on to a new identity” as part of the
47
48 transitional process. Turner (1977) describes this process as being “situationally and temporarily set
49
50 apart” from others. The transition induces identity tensions and paradoxes, since untested
51
52 projections of a future self are often not able to keep up with well-grounded and historically defined
53
54 self-images (Gabriel et al. 2010). The main scene in this narrative is defined by several events that
55
56 trigger the separation and resulting paradox: redundancy, constructive dismissal, or unfulfilling
57
58
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60

1
2 (temporary) jobs.

3
4 [When] I left I didn't want people to think there was a problem. So that's why I said I was
5 retiring. I am old, you see, and no one asked questions. What I was really intending was for [a]
6 sabbatical to see what my next step would be. Never thought that would be the end of the line
7 [but] I fell off a cliff. I've been out of work now for 16 months, working on my own stuff. But
8 my plan was to take a 12-month break from employment. To sort myself out... not sure I have.
9 (HF, 63, PRIME Trainer)
10
11
12

13 In the OEE identity narratives, an initial separation from a previous identity or social position tends
14 to be followed by a phase of experimentation in which OEE try out different forms of temporary
15 attachment to other groups or identities (Ibarra and Obudaru 2016). This process entails constant
16 self-questioning and reflection (Beech 2011), along with reacting to (or absorbing) external
17 influences and perceptions. This 'betwixt and between' transition status is inherently paradoxical.
18 Most of our OEE report spending some time still intensely involved with their old work identity
19 (although it may no longer be relevant), while they start to become committed to, yet are unsure
20 about, what their new future holds. Thus, we found a tension between them maintaining coherence
21 with a previous work identity and immersing themselves into what the new, potential
22 entrepreneurial identity requires from them.
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36 I was and I still am very wedded to the NHS (National Health Service, U.K.)... [Leaving the job,]
37 I felt rejected, redundant... But, when you stop being a consultant, you can't default into thinking
38 'I am just a pair of spare hands'. So, I am still a consultant, but people have to know what you
39 stand for and they expect a maverick. So, I need to identify a business or a product or service,
40 build a team, find the market, get everything to work and then move on, and then maybe find
41 another one and do the same thing! So, maybe I can do that as a doctor or consultant, but might
42 need to become something new. (JS, 57, Business Consultant to NHS)
43
44
45

46 The paradox of being both ex-employee and future entrepreneur is also present in the position the
47 'other' –e.g., family, friends, employers, the proximal community– is given in this narrative. On the
48 one hand, as ex-employees, OEE feel rejected, dismissed and forgotten by ex-employers. At the
49 same time, the 'other' is positioned as 'demanding' them to perform, find another job, achieve
50 clarity in purpose, and answer the question 'who are you?'. As a response, OEE report both trying
51 to advance their new ventures and re-engaging in traditional job search practices, such as applying
52 for jobs in the same employment area, revising CVs, and revisiting old contacts and networks.
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1
2 It is a very hard psychological process and you need support, almost like Alcoholics
3 Anonymous, to acknowledge 'I'm terrified' or 'I'm worried about the bottom line and whether I
4 am going to be eating through the bottom line'. It's so scary, I get panic attacks all the time. And
5 my family and friends still expect you to perform. But this is something I really want because I
6 am qualified to do it, not because I can play the corporate game. Because if I'm going to do that I
7 might as well be qualified as an accountant and get a regular pay cheque. The job that I do now
8 is so haphazardously paid that I only do it because I like it and it is me, not because I can bring in
9 what I call 'a corporate life style'. There is no point. But it is difficult to convince family,
10 friends. They need to trust you. You need to trust you. (MS, 52, Life Coach)
11

12
13
14 The narratives reporting these identity tensions are anchored in particular images of what it is to be
15 an entrepreneur or an employee. The entrepreneur's qualities of "resourcefulness, nimbleness [and]
16 subtle cunning" (Bird 1992: 207) are portrayed as opposed to the routine, disillusion, but safety
17 (Jones and Spicer 2010) of traditional employment roles. Indeed, while our interviewees describe
18 entrepreneurs as more creative, innovative and freer than the more traditional employees,
19 employment lures them back with the potential of safety, regularity (Tomlinson and Colgan 2014),
20 and better pay (Shane 2009).
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30 At the age of 57-years-old, I was made redundant. I am struggling to make enough money to
31 keep my head above water and, in fact, am going to have to ask my mother, who is in her
32 eighties, to help me out financially. As a single person, I have no partner to help and no savings.
33 I had a job that gave me an identity and, without it, I found myself floundering. But it was
34 something with music and people with disabilities that I wanted to do, so I am rediscovering the
35 passion and the excitement of doing something new, entrepreneurial, with social value. (ANH,
36 58, Music Teacher)
37
38

39 In the above stories, the tension is between going back to their 'employment' identity and trying
40 something new. The concept of liminality is applicable here if we attend to what happens at the
41 point of passage between these two identities and social positions. The narratives above outline
42 what Turner (1977) calls the 'betwixt and between' nature of liminality and help us to grasp what
43 OEE experience when becoming 'stuck' in a liminal situation. In our case, when the two identities
44 and social positions of (ex-)employee and potential entrepreneur overlap, they interfere with one
45 another and our OEE find themselves caught up in the 'noise' between their different demands.
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58 ***4.2. Interruption and polarization: Between the experienced and the creative self***

59 The competing demands of the overlapping identities and social positions outlined above present
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1
2 OEE with the equivalent of two mutually contradictory directives. As OEE enter into a liminal
3
4 transition, they move from a clear logic of being either an employee or an entrepreneur to a paradox
5
6 logic that includes being both, e.g., an ex-NHS consultant and a potential self-employed advisor. At
7
8 the liminal stage, however, the tension between those two identities and social positions becomes
9
10 experienced not so much as both/and but as neither/nor in the sense that our OEE feel neither
11
12 employees nor (yet) entrepreneurs. This identity tension sets the main scene in the polarization
13
14 narratives. The tension also generates frustration and attempts to find a quick escape from the
15
16 confusion of this liminal phase so that OEE can involve themselves again with a workable and clear
17
18 identity and social position, with recognisable limits. Engaging in some of the entrepreneurship
19
20 activities, such as looking for a loan to start the business or networking to extend their social
21
22 capital, brings the paradox and consequent frustration to the surface.

23
24
25
26
27 There are quite a lot of loans available when I go online... free interest loans and dah dah
28
29 dah...but HOW AM I GOING TO PAY THAT BACK? I do not have a job, I am not employed, I
30
31 cannot bring collateral, and I am 'too old' for them, so I might not have the time to pay that loan
32
33 back. And a lot of these networks also assume that you can drive quite long distances and all
34
35 assume you have computers and so on. You really have to fight the feeling of being not able,
36
37 lacking money, too old, lacking time, and end up thinking that maybe it is better to just go for
38
39 'normal' retirement. Become retired. (JS, 57, Photographer).

40
41 Within these narratives, OEE position themselves as initially 'paralyzed'. The paradox of having to
42
43 be both an ex-employee who needs to use their career experience, networks, and social capital
44
45 (Davidsson and Honig 2003), while at the same time 'reinventing oneself', being creative and
46
47 'young' if they are to succeed in becoming entrepreneurial (Rigolizzo and Amabile 2015),
48
49 'paralyses' them to the extent that it confuses and interferes with the flows of experience and
50
51 activity ordinarily channelled by, and into, their previous clear social positions and identities.

52
53 [F]rankly, so far, it has been difficult for me to keep body and soul together doing self-employed
54
55 work. The difficulty I've got at the moment is that I'm still — I suppose, really, the spanner was
56
57 I wasn't expecting so many people to turn around to me, when I left, and say, 'We've got a job
58
59 for you. Come and be employed by us'. Every time you go into a patch where there isn't much
60
work, you think to yourself, 'Wow, was that my last job? When will I start again? Can I do this
at my age?' (AM, 59, Business Consultant)

The 'other' is also portrayed as demanding 'youth' and using age as an exclusionary marker. The

1
2 paradox of having to be both experienced ex-employees and ‘fresh’ to become new entrepreneurs
3
4 results in a polarisation of OEE behaviour as they seek to escape their predicament of
5
6 indeterminacy by forcing a solution that conforms to one of the identities and social positions they
7
8 are caught between.
9

10
11 People tell you that as you get older you do get tired more quickly. But being able to [do] my
12
13 own thing can really re-energise me. It is true that when you are young, you are much more of a
14
15 risk taker. Then, you become risk adverse, [aware of] everything negative, and are scared of
16
17 being a failure. But, as an entrepreneur, you have to become a risk taker. Whether by the time
18
19 you are 65 you are more cautious and wise, but you still need to be going for [development]. The
20
21 thing is, there’s a risk in whatever you do. There are also risks in doing nothing. So, I rather go
22
23 for as much development and risk I can stomach. At least I tried. (SD, 70, Commercial Mentor)

24
25 The main cultural image of entrepreneurship guiding this narrative, and against which OEE fight to
26
27 adjust and find legitimacy, is one of ‘youth’. The ‘entrepreneurship as a youthful endeavour’
28
29 narrative (Ainsworth and Hardy, 2008) questions if the ‘old’ can be creative, innovative and playful.

30
31 Against this framing of the process of entrepreneurship, OEE struggle to overcome a ‘narrative
32
33 foreclosure’ that implies that, by virtue of being older, the story of their working lives is ‘essentially
34
35 over’ (Freeman 2010: 3). A common response is trying to become ‘younger’, following ‘successful
36
37 ageing’ (Andrews 2009) narratives.

38
39 The thing about when you get older, people’s excuses for not giving you the job or the funding
40
41 become more annoying. You know it’s a numbers’ game and you just think they want a pretty
42
43 girl on the left or the young ambitious guy on the right. And the danger is that you try to become
44
45 ‘younger’ to convince the bank manager to give you a loan for the business. I found myself
46
47 dying my hair, thinking of losing weight, dressing younger when going to those interviews and
48
49 that is a losing game, it just didn’t happen. So, after a particularly painfully unsuccessful one, I
50
51 decided to rethink what I was good at and started putting my age and my experience forward, not
52
53 hiding it. (LH, 60, Head of Charity)

54
55 As Turner (1977) indicated, the liminal phase in a ritual transition is designed to maximise the
56
57 propensity for participants to become ‘affected’, so that old identities and social positions may be
58
59 relinquished and new ones acquired, and so that personal dispositions may be aligned with the
60
61 requirements of the individual’s new role (Stenner et al. 2011). The stories above show how, in the
62
63 actual, on-going practice of entrepreneuring, personal identities and entrepreneuring activities are
64
65 thoroughly intertwined and inseparable. However, the narratives also show how significant changes
66

1
2 within and between social positions and activities can lead to entrepreneurial identities and
3
4 activities being de-coupled.

5
6 With regard to identity work, in a liminal situation, the basic questions of ‘who are you?’ (the
7
8 point of view of the other) and ‘who am I?’, which usually form an inseparable unity, can become
9
10 distinctly problematic and ‘out of joint’. Furthermore, the identity work tensions expressed in this
11
12 polarization narrative indicate that starting a shift in subjective position (‘who am I?’) is not enough
13
14 to make the identity transition real for OEE. The shift in position needs to be intersubjectively
15
16 recognised. Thus, any OEE who is to transit successfully to a new identity and social position
17
18 expresses the need to be recognised as a legitimate entrepreneur by other key social actors,
19
20 presupposing the question ‘who are you?’ The first question (‘who am I?’) challenges the OEE to
21
22 make the identity transition personally real, while the second (‘who are you?’) challenges them to
23
24 make it socially real.
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32 ***4.3. Pattern shift: Entrepreneurship as a moratorium or an art form***

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34 Research indicates that entrepreneurial identities develop through a variety of relational processes,
35
36 from the micro circles of daily interactions to the macro circles of today’s globalised economy and
37
38 society that shape and mould emergent entrepreneurs’ identities and practices (Phillips et al. 2013).
39
40 But, OEE are not simply determined from the outside in a top-down way by these relational circles.
41
42 OEE must also appropriate them as best they can into their personal spheres of action and
43
44 understanding, integrating what they encounter into something meaningful and actionable (Stenner
45
46 et al. 2011). From this perspective, each new circle OEE enter involves a passage through which
47
48 they are transformed. With each new transition, they are faced with reconciling what they once
49
50 were with what they might become, and, hence, with a task of integration through which they widen
51
52 their personal circle. However, these circles can also become vicious. Instead of ever widening, they
53
54 can be ever tightening, and occasions of transition or transformation can become ‘troubled’.
55
56
57

58
59 Future? From a perspective of future and what I’m going to do after, retirement is not retirement,
60 not an option, never going to be zero work. I’ll be working less. So, if today I’m working 8 hours

1
2 a day, maybe when I'm 70 I'll be working 4 or 8 hours in a week. But, I'll need to be working in
3 whatever, enough to be able to feed myself. 60 is not very old any more. Now that people have
4 to work 'til 67, if you're out of work at 50, say, that's 16 years on the job scene, okay. Forever.
5 That's an awful long time on very low money. (MBR, 60, Copy Writer)
6
7

8 The identity tension we find in these narratives is between starting a business as a 'slower' way to
9 retire and really developing something new and worthwhile. OEE use the images of pre-retired or
10 craft(wo)man to position themselves in these narratives. The term 'moratorium', as used in relation
11 to working identities by Gabriel et al. (2010), describes the kind of socially acceptable limbo-land
12 of experimentation that some OEE position themselves in, where self-employment, early retirement,
13 short-term ad hoc work, and returning to education and training are all featured as possible options.
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22 My pension is rubbish. I cannot retire now at 55. My husband is already retired. And if I were to
23 do something until I am 70, which is what it is looking like, I really need to do something that
24 could make a difference to the world and hopefully give me some remuneration at the end of it.
25 Now, it might need to be retraining or any short-term work, or becoming a volunteer. So, this is a
26 chance to think about who I am, what I enjoy, and do it. Good thing I do not have dependants
27 right now. If not, it would have been much more difficult. (BH, 55, Carer)
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29
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31 An alternative positioning for the self emerges when OEE imagine a different 'ending' beyond
32 retirement. Becoming 'older' is then used as the situation that allows them to consider their lives in
33 a new light and keep possibilities open against particular grand entrepreneuring narratives.
34 Becoming 'older' enables them to start reconfiguring their life space and reshuffle both proximal
35 (e.g., family and friends) and distal (e.g., community) spheres of experience.
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42 I was 74 at the time—a long time ago—I was born in 1933. I was developing a game for blind
43 people and the partially sighted. I called it Dunes. I got an award at GWIIN for that. Retired or
44 not, I'm still working on that. It's been through a lot of prototypes, a lot of development, until
45 eventually I think I've got the sort of thing that the market wants. But, I need cash to develop the
46 prototype, so I've just taken equity release out on my flat in [a London suburb]. Yes, I've had to
47 consider life expectancy, actuarial tables in the process of getting equity release, so I am aware
48 that I've got a certain limit of time, not a lot left. [But,] it makes me feel good. I'm a bit of an
49 artist and if I don't do this, what do I do? And the gaming community doesn't care. (SP, 83,
50 Games Designer)
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52
53

54 When the paradox of being old but having to become 'fresh' to succeed entrepreneurially cannot
55 easily be escaped using existing resources, it can push those involved towards the invention of new
56 identities and social positions within which the paradox can be re-signified. This presents the
57 possibility of a pattern shift. For Strauss (2017: 94-95), this is a 'dawning', the slow process of
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‘coming to realize’ that things are different in response to a ‘confounded expectation or a turning point’, which leads to a ‘heightened noticing’ of a new meaning. Dawning is not re-labelling, but having an experience anew. The OEE who can bear to linger in this liminal space/time seem to enjoy a distinctive and complex experience that might form the emergent basis of a new identity and social position.

I fear to have 30 or 40 years sitting at home reading books, if you’re lucky and you’ve got a library still working. So 30, 40 years literally doing nothing. My brain shrivels at that thought. So, for me, to keep going, maybe the self-validation is most important because I couldn’t conceive not doing anything. So, it is a question of how best to use my skills and energy for as long as I can. So, you start adjusting. I now have a powerful looking business card, a title, I dress smartly, and I do what they now are calling ‘fake it ‘til you make it’. Old or not, I’m on it. I’m enjoying the challenge and I am learning. (EN, 54, Film Producer)

If liminality is the condition of being caught in the dimension between two mutually exclusive identity alternatives (in this case being older and being entrepreneurial) and becoming potentially paralysed by the contradiction between them, the potential pattern shift our analysis outlines involves the re-signification of this contradiction in the context of a new identity and social position.

In my industry, a woman is really ancient at 55 and so I wasn’t quite sure that it was a great time to be starting a business. You just look around you and everyone’s 20, 25 years younger than me, sitting there in coffee shops with their laptops with headphones in. I thought, ‘oh, maybe I’m a bit too old’. But then, I don’t think I am. I know all the clients and I know them very well and have done for some time; and, second, I am me, you know? I can do, can sell, can create. And that does not depend on being a number. It is a skill, a craft. (KB, 60, IT Support Engineer)

It is here that we can talk about a sense of identity re-aggregation, which follows a transition where one does not return to ‘normal’ but is gradually able to construct a new identity (Ibarra and Obodaru 2016) and move to a new understanding of self and community (Turner 1977; van Gennep 1960). The re-aggregation, incorporation, or post-liminal rite is the ultimate end point in the transition. Not all OEE reach this point, but some seemed ready to move into this re-aggregation state. However, for this change to be real, it requires a social recognition of the new skills and qualities of OEE. It also requires that the change is not just an externally imposed categorization, but that it “touch[es] the core of what it means to be human” (Thomassen 2013: 7).

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2 There are SO many variables and sometimes it makes me question why I am doing this and
3 whether it is worth it. It eventually will be. You have to remain positive. You have to believe in
4 what you're doing so much that a negative here and there doesn't affect that belief. And you
5 have to be very patient, craft it. I know that because I am old. It's not going to work if you're
6 impatient. Being old has its advantages. You know how to let everyone else do their own thing
7 and feed that into you. I am beyond competition. Working for me is a pleasure, need to do and
8 need to believe. Your belief has to be that strong that other people think you're in denial. (SD,
9 70, Commercial Mentor)
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13 What the narratives outlined above bring clearly forward is the tension between potential and actual
14 identities for OEE. Furthermore, the narratives indicate that any liminal transition between identities
15 and social positions will require OEE to make investments both at the psychological and the social
16 activity levels and to manage the interruptions associated with such important transitions. Such
17 changes of condition do not occur without "disturbing the life of society and the individual" (van
18 Gennep, 1960: 13). Because social positions and activities are tightly coupled with the identities of
19 the OEE who must continuously enact them, any transition in social position requires a
20 corresponding shift in identity. This is fundamentally a temporal issue, since it poses challenges for
21 OEE who are facing both past and future identities and social positions at the same time. In facing
22 the past, OEE must extricate themselves from the understandings and activities of a now redundant
23 identity and social position. Facing the future, on the other hand, OEE rarely slot frictionlessly into
24 a new identity; they must learn to inhabit it and that means familiarizing themselves with the new
25 habitat it affords, and creatively modifying it according to desires and capabilities. In liminal
26 conditions, the past exerts its inertia just at the moment when the future challenges their
27 adaptability.
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49 **5. Discussion**

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51 In recent years, OEE have become a target category for employment research and policies in many
52 European countries. In the E.U., in particular, employment policies promoting early retirement from
53 the workforce are losing legitimacy and being replaced by measures that encourage older workers to
54 remain in the labour force for longer (Foden and Jepsen 2002). Debates have centred around two
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1
2 related concepts: extending working lives, through keeping people in employment up until or
3
4 beyond state retirement/pension ages; and reversing the ‘one-way street’ (OECD 2006: 10) of early
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6 exit, thus, getting unemployed or economically inactive older people back into work. But most
7
8 people in their 50s are not ready to overhaul their social and financial positions, as well as reinvent
9
10 themselves, to become entrepreneurial, so we need to have an understanding of employment and
11
12 entrepreneuring that accounts for developments after 50 (Stenner et al. 2011). In our research, we
13
14 have seen how OEE are challenged to develop as entrepreneurs without experiential knowledge of
15
16 what that identity means or what a social position as entrepreneur entails. We have used a liminal
17
18 approach to study entrepreneurial identity development to better understand how OEE navigate
19
20 identity paradoxes they face in their personal transitions towards entrepreneurship.
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22

23
24 Entrepreneurship itself is often viewed as a transition or stage distinct from other areas of
25
26 business (e.g., Shane and Venkataraman 2000). Recognising that ‘entre’ refers to an ‘in between’,
27
28 Steyaert (2005) argues that entrepreneurship should be viewed as a border zone. As our analysis
29
30 shows, the transition into entrepreneurship by OEE is ultimately a liminal, transformative condition,
31
32 a process of creating possible futures and states of being, while they live “in that half-way house of
33
34 becoming” (Anderson 2005: 598), existing as would-be entrepreneurs. In starting their
35
36 entrepreneurial journey, OEE find themselves ‘temporarily undefined’ in between social orders as
37
38 they move from one phase to another. In between lies a liminal phase of transition, where they
39
40 accept they have moved beyond their earlier roles but have not yet acquired the new entrepreneurial
41
42 one. This phase is characterised by ambiguity since, from Turner (1977), they are beyond the
43
44 normative social structure with little or no access to ‘schemes of classification’ that indicate one’s
45
46 position in a cultural space (Eriksson-Zetterquist 2008).
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52 Furthermore, we have seen that an important characteristic of liminality is that it is paradoxically
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54 defined by what it is not (Turner 1977). The OEE liminal ‘border zone’ is characterized by a
55
56 general sense of confusion and ambiguity. Our analysis shows how OEE in their liminal period
57
58 confront paradoxes, interruptions, and attempted activity and identity pattern shifts. Confronting the
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60

1 paradox of having to both be ‘experienced’ using their career skills, networks, and social capital
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3
4 (Davidsson and Honig 2003), while at the same time ‘reinventing themselves’, being creative and
5
6
7 ‘youthful’ if they are to succeed in becoming entrepreneurial (Rigolizzo and Amabile 2015)
8
9 confuses and interferes with the flows of experience and activity ordinarily channelled by, and into,
10
11 their previous clear social positions and identities.
12

13
14 Once rendered salient, we have seen how paradoxical identity tensions stimulate either positive
15
16 or negative responses in the form of diverse narrative positions. Paradox literature proposes
17
18 temporal and spatial splitting techniques (e.g., Poole and Van de Ven 1989) that mirror those
19
20 demonstrated in the case of our OEE. While some OEE see their entrepreneuring journey as a
21
22 moratorium, as a bridging in-between activity before ‘full retirement’, others see entrepreneuring as
23
24 an art, an activity requiring full engagement, patience and skill. Likewise, we have seen how OEE’s
25
26 paradoxical approaches to entrepreneurial identity might include strategies that try to overcome or
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28 accommodate tensions (Lewis 2000), like embracing both older and entrepreneurial identities as
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30 distinct, yet mutually enabling and avoiding tendencies toward a preferred mode that may become
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32 self-reinforcing toward a dangerous extreme. Such identity work efforts aid self-directed action
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34 (Gabriel 1999) by engaging OEE as agents to reflect and act upon their own identity tensions
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36 (Zanoni and Janssens 2007). To do so, OEE engage in identity work to navigate the tensions
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38 prompting feelings of confusion, contradiction, and self-doubt leading to a constant examination of
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40 the self and ‘others’ (Lutgen-Sandvik 2008), particularly in relation to the entrepreneuring journey.
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47 As Szokolczai (2009) suggests, the process of identity work and identification with particular
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49 groups, organizations or modes of existence might be a way to search for meaning in liminal
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51 conditions. Identity work is indeed a way to link oneself to a role, a position and/or a place in the
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53 collective by force of our own being and emotional involvement. As such, it may be a most blatant
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55 method of indoctrination, and it has been analysed as such by Foucault (Strozier 2002). However,
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57 while identity work is not the only ‘way out’ from a liminal condition, it can be a way to tie oneself
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59 to a new identity, and thus a potential way out of the spinning wheel of liminality. We have seen in
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1
2 our identity narrative analysis how OEE take and assign narrative identity positions to themselves
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4 and others (van Langenhove and Harré 1999) when describing their transition and how those
5
6 positions relate to particular images, narratives, and practices of entrepreneurship through which
7
8 they ‘do’ and ‘redo’ entrepreneuring (Steyaert 2007). For instance, entrepreneuring is seen
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10 variously as risky, creative, ‘young’ persons’ work, or ‘art form’ throughout the different narratives
11
12 where OEE portray themselves also in a diversity of positions from ex-employees to crafts(wo)men.
13
14 Thus, as the OEE confront identity paradoxes and their identity narrative position changes, their
15
16 perception of entrepreneuring, along with the way they act, changes too. Those OEE who manage to
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18 accept the identity interruptions and polarization that their transition brings seem to move away
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20 from an initial sense of isolation and are able to bring a creative understanding to entrepreneuring
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22 processes.
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27 Echoing notions of creativity inherent in liminality, Steyaert (2005: 7) views the entrepreneurial
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29 border zone as “a fertile middle space. ...a heterotopic space for varied thinking”. Thus, lying outside
30
31 the mainstream, the liminal state allows for liberation from routine social structures, norms of
32
33 behaviour, and other expectations (Tempest and Starkey 2004). This indicates that liminal periods
34
35 can also be periods of increased creativity and innovation, as those involved take advantage of the
36
37 additional freedoms and lack of constraints. When the paradox of being old but having to become
38
39 ‘fresh’ cannot easily be escaped using existing resources, it can push those involved towards
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41 acceptance and ultimately the invention of new identities and social positions. This presents OEE
42
43 with the possibility of a pattern shift. Liminality, therefore, may lead to a sense of autonomy and
44
45 personal freedom, as OEE start to transcend institutional and social constraints. Such position can
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47 enhance opportunities for creative thinking as, unbound by structural procedures (Garsten 1999),
48
49 individuals challenge existing boundaries (Sturdy et al. 2006a) so fostering deviation and originality
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51 (Turner 1977). Thus, it is in conditions of liminality where we find that alternative and creative
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53 understandings tip the balance and prompt pattern shifts, allowing OEE to develop into new
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55 identities, activities, and social positions as entrepreneurs.
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2 Therefore, from a liminal perspective, entrepreneuring can be conceptualized as an on-going
3 generative process emerging from the interdependence between the OEE's personal liminal
4 transitions and their engagement in a particular sociocultural context (Garcia-Lorenzo et al. 2018).
5
6 As the identity work tensions expressed by OEE indicate, starting a shift in subjective position
7 ('who am I?') is not enough to make the identity transition real. The shift in identities and social
8 positions also needs to be intersubjectively recognised. As Anderson, Drakopoulou-Dodd and Jack
9 (2012) state, entrepreneuring is very much about the process of becoming, and becoming is always
10 a co-production between the entrepreneur, the generalised other, and their historical and cultural
11 contexts.
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23 Finally, our research also illustrates how, like other identity categories, age works as a master
24 signifier to shape ways of thinking, being and doing, establishing what we can see as reality and
25 truth, and both creating and constraining meanings related to age (Gilleard and Higgs 2013). We
26 have seen how some OEE talk about actively 'keeping young', trying to fulfil the demands of
27 'successful ageing', imitating the 'young guns' with the risk of alienation (Freeman 2010; Stenner,
28 McFarquhar, and Bowling 2011), or fighting a 'narrative foreclosure' in which they gather the
29 conviction that the story of their working lives is "essentially over" (Freeman 2010: 3). However,
30 we have also seen how new, creative understandings can be developed among OEE, where being
31 older is explained as a potentially generative economic, organizational, and psychological structure.
32 Some of our OEE use imagination to consider their lives in a new light and keep possibilities open,
33 without falling into particular grand narratives that in many cases constrain, rather than enable,
34 them to transition successfully into entrepreneurship. Getting old for them while engaging in an
35 entrepreneurial process means a reconfiguration of the life space, a reshuffling of spheres of
36 experience, both proximal and distal. Because these are new, reconfigured or transformed, there is
37 learning, identity transformation, and, through imagination, renewed sense making and new ways of
38 doing. In their liminal identity narratives, our OEE look hard at what makes a life and start to
39 address differently, and protect, those spaces that allow development during their whole life-course,
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2 using cultural and social resources to attempt pattern shifts in their identities and social activities.
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6 **6. Conclusions**

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9 In this paper, we have illustrated, empirically, how OEE experience the transition from diverse
10 forms of employment into entrepreneurship from a liminal identity work perspective. We see the
11 contributions of our research as threefold.
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16 First, in uncovering the liminality inherent in OEE transitions, our research captures how older
17 entrepreneurship is becoming one of the paradoxical identity directives typical of current work
18 conditions. While the paradoxical nature of these liminal injunctions has long been identified, the
19 implications of living that paradox and trying to overcome it in generative ways have rarely been
20 addressed. A paradox lens has enabled us to take a more holistic, fluid, both/and framing of identity
21 tensions among OEE. Through identity work, OEE are able to position older and entrepreneurial
22 identities as two sides of the same coin, rather than as polarized contradictions. Such framing
23 reduces anxiety, enabling acceptance and appreciation of tensions. The resulting mind-set helps
24 OEE cope with ambiguity inherent in entrepreneurial transitions. Our research on the liminal
25 transitions of OEE opens new research questions in this respect.
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39 Second, our research reinforces and extends the 'process view' (Steyaert 2007: 454) of
40 entrepreneuring, illustrating how entrepreneuring is experienced as an on-going generative process
41 emerging from the interdependence between our OEE entrepreneurs and their sociocultural context.
42
43 In particular, our research illustrates the adaptive and fluid nature of the narratives and practices
44 involved in emergent entrepreneuring, and underscores the fluidity, and the on-going and piecemeal
45 everyday work of such organizing processes (Barinaga 2016). This perspective allows us to go
46 beyond the essentialist and equilibrium-based notions underpinning both the opportunity discovery
47 perspective (Venkataraman et al. 2012) and the evolutionary perspective (Aldrich and Martinez
48 2001) in entrepreneurship. Our research particularly positions OEE as part of an overall process of
49 personal and social change beyond purely economic logics (Jones and Spicer 2010).
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2 Third, our research has clear implications for policy making. Scholars and policy makers
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4 increasingly emphasize that supporting older entrepreneurs can be a good strategy to tackle the
5
6 socio-economic challenges emerging from an ageing population (Kautonen et al. 2011). However,
7
8 as our research shows, OEE encounter discrimination and find it difficult to fit within narratives that
9
10 frame entrepreneurship as an activity for younger individuals. Our research also resonates with
11
12 previous studies that found ageist expectations emerge not only from within institutional and
13
14 societal discourses (Mallet and Wapshott 2015), but also from social reference groups (family,
15
16 friends and clients), which can affect OEE efforts to develop themselves and their businesses. A
17
18 suggestion to supporting older entrepreneurship is to create more tailored training programs (Dennis
19
20 2011) and entrepreneurial development systems (Lichtenstein and Lyons 2012), where supporters
21
22 and coaches can address the diversity of older entrepreneurs' backgrounds and skills, and the
23
24 emerging contextual barriers at various institutional and social levels. This is of particular
25
26 importance in countries where government has recently decided to increase the state pensionable
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28 age and where, in many cases, private pensions fail to deliver adequate returns for a comfortable
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30 retirement (Wainwright and Kibler 2014). As such, there seems to be an increasing need to
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32 understand further how older individuals can engage in the labour market for longer, and how we
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34 can help them to develop their small businesses further.
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Table 1: Older entrepreneurs' transitional identity narratives

Key narrative identity tensions and liminal dimensions.	Self-positioning	Position of the 'other' in relation to entrepreneuring	Images of entrepreneurship regulating the narratives	Examples of entrepreneuring practices reported in the narratives
<i>In-between identity continuity and innovation: Entrepreneurial vs. organizational self</i>	Ex-employee	Rejecting through dismissal, redundancy or unfulfilling jobs	<i>Entrepreneurship as risky, uncertain, dangerous</i>	Applying for jobs in the same employment area Revising CVs and revisiting old contacts and networks Shaping current start-up according to old work identity Looking for a 'proper' job in 'low times' at start-up
	Defining self through previous work identity	Supporting the process of finding a new job		
<i>Encountering Paradox</i>	Potential entrepreneur	Resistant to the new potential identity	<i>Entrepreneurship as creative, innovative, emergent</i>	Looking for training and mentors to become self-employed Drafting alternative careers and business plans, developing a 'name' or brand
	In on-going self-reflection mode: 'What am I good for?'	Demanding: 'Who are you? What can you do?'	<i>Entrepreneurs as 'mavericks'</i>	Looking for physical location for business (e.g., shop, office)
<i>Experience vs. creativity: Older vs. younger entrepreneuring</i>	Lacking 'youth'	Demanding 'youth' to fund, enable or support a business	<i>Entrepreneurship as young people's business</i>	Looking for funding to develop business Trying to 'become' young: by changing image, habits, behaviour
	Experienced after many years of employment	<i>Acknowledging experience but expecting 'freshness' to provide legitimacy</i>	<i>Entrepreneurship needs legitimation from the community</i>	Looking for proximal/distal social support to fully embrace entrepreneurship Foregrounding the 'experienced' image
<i>Emerging (older) entrepreneurs: Moratorium vs. craft</i>	Moratorium: Pre-retired entrepreneur	Supporting some activity to manage 'ageing'	<i>Entrepreneurship as bridging in-between activity before 'full retirement'</i>	Entrepreneurship as temporal, part-time work Combining entrepreneuring with other non-business activities
	Entrepreneur as craft(wo)man	Accepting full involvement in a new venture	<i>Entrepreneurship as an activity requiring full engagement, patience and skill</i>	Entrepreneurship as crafting a business Full engagement
<i>Engaging in (Potential) pattern shifts</i>				